

Philanthropy and Economy Development: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract: This Study aims to retrieve journal, articles, books related to Philanthropy or Charity over a span of 8 years and purpose new pathways for future research. The study involved systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis of 533 publication on the subject registered in the Scopus database from 2015 to 2022. The bibliometric procedure evaluates research performance and progress within an international impact framework, while VOS viewer visualize overall research trends in philanthropy. The results of the study show that United States is the country with the most publications related to philanthropy and economic development Deng.G, and Huang, C.C are the two leading authors in this field based on the total number of publications and citations. Some of the author's most recent keywords include "Sustainable development"; Charity; "Corporate Philanthropy"; Philanthropy; Donation, which shows a strong current interest in the study of Philanthropy. This paper is useful to academics, organizations and policymakers in understanding the general picture of the field of philanthropy and allows future researchers to see where this study started and trace its shifts over time.

Keywords: Philanthropy, Development of Economy, Corporate Funding, Donation

Introduction

This article focuses on the role that large indigenous nonprofit organizations play in the socioeconomic development of developing countries. We explore how and why these organizations are established and grow in strength to serve a sizable portion of the underprivileged population in unequal societies. The principal remedy for persistent economic and social inequities is provided in much development literature, which focuses on the obligations of wealthier countries to less developed ones (Holcombe, 2014; Sua´rez & Gugerty, 2016). In nations like Pakistan, there is comparatively little scholarship devoted to local philanthropy or social entrepreneurship. We aim to contribute to the rectification of this inequity. Finding indigenous solutions to socio-economic issues may be a better strategy in a world when foreign aid is being distributed more sparingly (Appe & Pallas, 2018).

Increasing the well-being of collectives, such as social groupings, communities, and nations, in a sustainable manner is the process of socio-economic development. Sen (1999) claims that socioeconomic change is a procedure that prioritizes individual liberties, expanded opportunities for people to improve their lives for they result from expanded freedoms. Sen contends that prolonged poverty, starvation, disease, and illiteracy are all closely correlated with a lack of freedom; as a result, it is important to abolish any restrictions on freedom. Economic, social, political, and cultural freedoms are requirements that encourage human freedom (Nussbaum, 2003). These form the backbone of what Sen refers to as the capabilities approach and are interconnected and mutually supportive in promoting and influencing the development process. Hunger and poverty are abolished, people have access to money, and possibilities are available.

Social freedom is the absence of social ills and access to services like health care, education, clean water, and sanitation (Carothers & de Gramont, 2013)

Researchers are encouraged to conduct quantitative analyses of their scientific outputs to better understand the current "intellectual structure" as research in some disciplines of study develops (Rivera and Pizam, 2015). Through the development of a knowledge foundation, the identification of research trends, comprehension of the theory and technique employed, evaluation of the contributions made by the research, and formulation of prospective future research (Ferreira et al., 2014). Bibliometric a cutting-edge technique employed in this analysis that tries to expose the evolution, structure, and visualization of scientific production in a given field of study, is one of the novel techniques used (Mostafa, 2020; Qi et al., 2018).

However, there is a gap in the literature regarding the conceptual foundation of charity that needs to be filled. Therefore, this study uses a bibliometric network to look into scholarly articles on charity in an effort to address this gap. This method aids in tracing the conceptualization, progression, and growth of philanthropic concepts.

This study attempts to address a number of research concerns, such as: First, how is the advancement of philanthropic research? Second, what are the leading philanthropy-related authors, publications, and nations? Third, how is the

international network of writers, organizations and nations cooperating in the area of charitable research? What are the fourth question's intellectual framework and research theme developments in philanthropy? This study examines 533 Scopus articles on Islamic philanthropy that were published between 2015 and 2022 and involved the top 10 nations. This analysis aids in understanding philanthropy's growth, intellectual structure, and research contributions while also highlighting problems and promising topics for further study.

Design/methodology/approach

The research team has evaluated the idea of philanthropy in various industries by philanthropists (by using systematic literature review together with bibliometric analysis), since it has been correctly noted by previous researchers that learning is come from experience. A sum of 10290 articles extracted from Scopus database with the help of most relevant keywords selected for the study (Philanthropy, charity, donation, philanthropist) along with this AND word is used to add more

Keywords (Development, development of economy). Some filters are also added which include (Subject area, Document type, language, keywords, source type, publication stage and year wise).

Research methodology and data statistics

A thorough analysis of a few chosen publications considerably adds to the database of material already in existence. The right keyword selection is essential for systematic literature reviews.

Screening, gathering, organizing, drafting, and lastly presenting the results make up the five stages of this methodical procedure (Tatham et al., 2017). In the current work, a similar approach has been used to find several topics based on picked keywords, followed by a projection of future work scope with respect to a charitable organization. By collecting bibliographic data from other published papers in the particular discipline, bibliometric analysis is performed by analyzing the scholars' thinking through writing and citation (Zupic and Carter, 2015). By performing bibliometric analysis, it can be helpful to explore the topic of interest in particular discipline hence providing future directions for researchers (Khudzari et al., 2018).

Primary keywords and search results

The research team initially used a random selection of a few terms, including:- Philanthropy, Charity, donation, philanthropist, AND Development, "Development of economy" this keywords gives the result of 10,290 database. In the next step, some filters are used with this keywords to search the most relevant studies. This study aims to provide thorough bibliometric analysis of the patterns and trends in the scientific literature on innovation in philanthropy (Medias et al., 2023). By choosing one of the accessible databases, "systematic literature reviews" are pursued. The most well-known online databases are Science Direct, Web-of- Science, and SCOPUS. The Scopus database was chosen by the author for this particular piece of work. The biggest number of articles published across over 10290 journals ("Emerald", "Springer", "Taylor", "Wiley", "Elsevier", and "Francis") than any other online database is a plausible explanation.

The majority of publications that are now available are from a variety of disciplines, including business management and accounting, econometrics and finance, economics, and social science. The research team also concentrates on completely published items in the press (such as book chapters, review articles, books, conference papers, etc.). Information on contributing authors, publication year, article source, article affiliation, and article abstracts was provided by the identified papers.

Refining initial results

The next stage involves applying certain filters to the top search result, which include: (Subject- business, management and accounting; Language- English; Source-Journal, Book series, Book; Publication stage- Final; Filter by year- 2015 to 2022; Document type- Article, book chapter, review, book, conference paper; Keywords- Philanthropy, sustainable development, corporate social responsibility, sustainability, charities, non government organization, fundraising, social welfare, poverty, India, donation, economics, community development, corporate philanthropy, CSR, nonprofit organization, NGOs, crowd funding, charitable giving, donation, social development, developing countries, economic & social effect and commerce. 533 total documents received after using these filters. In this study the CSV file of 533 documents will be used. The present work purely focuses on philanthropy and its close connection with other related terms.

Descriptive statistics

Based on information from the Scopus database about philanthropy or charity and its related domain, descriptive statistics defines the majority of articles as "journal-wise" publication, "affiliation-wise" publication, the top 10 "country wise", "subject wise classification", yearly wise publication, and the top 20 funding sponsors. The very first description is about yearly publication of articles on Philanthropy and development of economy (refer to table 1 and figure 1). A huge contribution is evidence in the year 2021, followed by 2020. It can be seen that there is an increasing trend towards philanthropy in last year's but this trend break in the 2022 because no of publications in the year 2022 are less than no of publications in the year 2021.

Table 1: Yearly publication (Philanthropy)

Year	Document
2022	76
2021	86
2020	58
2019	77
2018	64
2017	51
2016	65
2015	50

Source: Scopus Database; 2022 to 2015

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Affiliation-wise description of articles present an interesting statistics for researcher(s) and academicians(s). This section shares list of topmost universities all around the world that are highly contributing towards research outputs in the area of philanthropy and development of economy. Most active universities include HKCU(7), MU(6), SMU(5) and The university of Manchester and sequence goes on (refer to table 2 and figure 2).

Every nation is interested with how its economy is developing and growing, which is somewhat tied to research-oriented activities. One of the most important indicators of growth in almost any country is an increase in research output. Growth along with development and research status of any country are linked to each other. Philanthropy activities are enhancing day by day in almost every single country but it can be seen that developed countries are more involved in charitable giving. The list of top 10 countries, which contribute or/are working towards philanthropy and sustainable development in the last 8 years of time is shared below. Top most countries are United States (132), United Kingdom (85), china (56), and for rest table 3 and figure 3 are consulted. The present analysis also discussed about the other countries that are lagging behind in this trend.

Table:3 Top 10 countries (philanthropy)

Country	Document
United States	132
United Kingdom	85
China	56
Australia	31
Canada	28
India	27
Germany	22
Spain	16
Malaysia	15
Russian Federation	15

Philanthropy and charity are become important now a days for sustainable growth and touched almost every aspect of human life, be it personal or professional. Diverse subjects one-way or the other connects themselves with technology. This section demonstrates number of publications in various subjects in combination with Economics and economy development. The aspect of philanthropy is covered most in Social science(377), business management, and accounting(231), environmental science(115), economics, econometrics and finance (113) and rest subject areas can be referred from table 4 and Figure 4.

Table 4: subject classification

Subject Area	Document
Social Science	377
Business, Management and accounting	231
Environmental science	115
Economics, Econometrics and Finance	113
Arts and Humanities	65
Energy	58
Engineering	42

Computer Science	36
Decision Science	16
Medicine	16
Psychology	15
Agricultural and Biological Science	10
Earth and Planetary Science	9
Mathematics	4
Health professions	3
Nursing	2
Materials Science	1
Physics and Astronomy	1

Documents by subject area

Scopus

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Financial support for research is the element that academics and researchers look forward to the most. The findings support the widespread sponsorship of philanthropic research by foundations, organizations, and sponsors in the form of research projects, consulting initiatives, doctoral degrees and post-doctoral academic fellowships, and other similar initiatives.

In last eight years, organizations that have provided funding include National Natural Science Foundation of China (11), Economic & Social Research Council (11), Ministry of Education of

the people’s Republic of China (7) and European Commission (5), and the list goes on (refer to table 5 and figure 5). The results can help future researchers(s) to approach for funding.

Table 5: Top 10 funding sponsors

The study of charity is at its height in a society where competition is expanding. Academics are also conducting the most research possible in this field. Table 6 and Figure 6 provide a list of the top 10 authors who are active in this field and have contributed to philanthropy and economic growth are Huang,C.C (5), Deng, G.(4), Zhou,H.(4),Harrow ,J.(3) and many more to come. The work contributed can be a good source of reference for future researchers.

Table 6: Top 10 Authors

Author	Document
Deng,G	4
Huang,CC	4
Zhou,H	4
Harrow. J	3

Jung.T	3
Shaul Bar Nissim, H.	3
Allah Pitchay, A.	2
Amponsah-Tawiah, K.	2
Borchgrevink, K.	2
Breen, O.B.	1

Documents by author

Scopus

Compare the document counts for up to 15 authors.

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Document per year by source

This analysis help to find out the source of published document with the respected year and also present the citation score of each source. A record of five source has been examined, which has large number of documents : Sustainability Switzerland has 11 document in the year 2022 with the citation score 5.8 , CSR Sustainability Ethics And Governance has 7 documents in the year 2016 with the citation score .7 , and rest subject areas can be referred from table 7 and Figure 7.

Table: List of top 5 sources

Source	Document
Sustainability Switzerland	40
CSR Sustainability Ethics and Governance	22
Voluntas	20
Foundation Review	12
Journal of Cleaner Production	9

Documents per year by source

Scopus

Compare the document counts for up to 10 sources. Compare sources and view CiteScore, SJR, and SNIP data

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Data analysis and findings

The analysis of the citations in the data from Scopus is covered in this section. The study team uses bibliometric analysis and systematic literature review to undertake citation analysis. VOS viewer is used for the former. Huge amounts of data can be handled by this software, which can also create files that can be utilized or transferred to other programs like "Pajek", "Gephi", and "Excel" (Persson and Schlichter, 2015). Results in the form of citation analysis and co-citation analysis are made possible. A content-based analysis is a cluster analysis. This analysis makes use of the VOS viewer. It aids in innovative visualization in a variety of vibrant shapes, which is important for visualization.

Bibliometric Mapping

Bibliometric mapping

Co-occurrence mapping and co-authorship mapping were the two sections of the analyses. Co-authorship refers to the interconnections of authors, contributing countries, or associations for the growth of research topics or areas, whereas co-occurrence, also known as a semantic network, refers to relationships among the terms.

All keywords were taken into account as the analysis unit in the co-occurrence mapping, with the help of the full counting approach. The analysis's scope was likewise restricted by the study. For instance, a keyword's minimum

number of occurrences was set as a limiting factor at five (5). Thus, out of 2868 keywords from 533 researches, only 133 meet the threshold.

The programs was used to analyze each term and calculate the links, overall link strengths, and co-occurrences of the keyword with other keywords. According to Guo et al. (2019), Links are used to describe when two items occur together, and the total link strength reflects all the references that have been cited between two items. Additionally, the occurrences show how many articles contained the keyword. The keywords with highest occurrence are shown in the table given below.

Sustainable development and donation in cluster 1, Sustainability and CSR in cluster 2, Philanthropy in cluster 3, Social welfare and Charities in cluster 4, Development and charity in Cluster 5, Corporate social responsibility in cluster 6 were among the most highly Co-occurring keywords with occurrence weights (total link strength) of 83(91), 27(21) from cluster 1, 59(94) and 28(46) from cluster 2, 143(148) from cluster 3, 22(15) and 21(14) from cluster 4, 30(56) and 26(15) from cluster 5, Corporate social responsibility 89(88) from cluster 6, respectively.

Table:1 Most highly co-occurring keywords.

Keywords	Cluster Number	Links	Total strength	Link	Occurrence
Charitable giving	1	6	7		11
Commerce	1	8	12		6
Crowd funding	1	15	26		23
Crowd sourcing	1	6	13		7
Donation	1	16	21		27
Eco.&Social	1	11	16		7
effect					
Equity	1	6	7		5
Finance		11	16		10
Fund Raising	1	13	23		20
NPO	1	16	26		15
Sustainable development	1	32	91		83
CSR	2	17	46		28
Economic development	2	18	33		14
Economies	2	10	13		10

Empowerment	2	14	20	5
Ethics	2	12	14	7
Rural development	2	8	9	5
SDGs	2	9	13	7
Stakeholder	2	10	16	7
Sustainability	2	33	94	59
SDGs	2	12	18	6
Educational development	3	8	14	5
Governance approach	3	17	43	21
Historical perspective	3	7	12	5
India	3	18	38	26
NGO	3	17	40	28

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Philanthropy	3	39	148	143
Social Change	3	7	11	6
Urban development	3	5	9	5
Charities	4	11	14	21
Donation	4	8	10	10
Funding	4	7	10	7
Government	4	14	23	12
NGOs	4	10	20	17
Social Capital	4	6	8	6
Social Welfare	4	12	15	22
Charity	5	18	15	26
Development	5	22	56	30
Inequality	5	6	8	5
Poverty	5	20	29	21
Religion	5	12	21	10
Social development	5	14	19	12
Social enterprise	5	15	22	13
Corporate Philanthropy	6	12	21	25
Corporate Social Responsibility	6	27	88	89
CSR	6	8	12	6
CSR activities	6	3	9	6

Moreover, in the first cluster, it was also shown that some aspects of exploration were included such as donation and crowdfunding. Crowdfunding offers a variety of alternatives for advancing a sustainable society, with a focus on sustainable businesses and innovators. In a study by Scataglini & Ventresca (2019), it is found that due to the lack of technological entry hurdles and the lack of SDG-focused crowdfunding platforms that now operate to the standards of successful platforms, the environment is ideal for the expansion of contribution crowdfunding in the future. These elements suggest that there is a chance to develop a new platform that is connected to the SDGs and in line with the recognized business practices. However, donation and crowdfunding have a great impact on the sustainable development including its contribution to economical and social factors. It should be noted that charitable giving, donation and crowdfunding entails massive efforts to achieve the sustainability and had an economic and social impact.

Cluster 2 green

The second cluster focused more on CSR, Ethics, rural development, empowerment, stakeholders, SDGs, economic development were the keywords with the highest Co-Occurrence weight of 28, 7, 5, 5, 7, 7, 14 respectively. Sustainability was more interlinked with the above keywords. Thus, it can be described in this result that CSR is very important for sustainable growth. Both CSR and business ethics are part of one another. It's the responsibility of corporates to take considerable initiatives for the sustainable growth of the community.

CSR frequently aims to increase societal welfare or increase the sustainability of corporate operations. CSR extends beyond adhering to contractual, legal, and regulatory standards (McWilliams and Siegel 2001), CSR initiatives and practices are therefore frequently voluntary, however they may also be motivated by strategic considerations or market forces (Kitzmueller and Shim shack 2012). Sustainability and CSR both focus on the three key areas of the surroundings, society, and economy. Sustainability emphasizes on taking action in these areas, whereas CSR is concentrated on reporting on them. There are numerous ways for organizations to help charitable causes. Acc. To Sanchez Teba et al. (2021), the emphasis on CSR, sustainability, and the environment have been the key driving forces behind the industry steady growth. Additionally, the examination of the various theme networks revealed a connection between CSR, sustainability, and business.

Further it will be concluded that Sustainability is related to some important theme:- Rural development, CSR, Ethics and empowerment of an economy. There is a link between these terms and the connections between sustainability, CSR, and the environment are getting thicker. They are more thoroughly encompassed by the field study, which strengthen their ties to therefore mentioned clusters.

Cluster 3 blue

The third cluster focused more on nongovernmental organization, educational development, government approach, social change. These were the keywords with the highest Co-occurrence weights of 28,5,21,6 respectively. Philanthropy was more interlinked with the keyword non- governmental organization (co-occurrence weight 143). Thus, it can be described in this result that growing interest in philanthropy was also inclining towards social change.

Philanthropy has a link with urban development and educational development. Further it is noted that philanthropy by nongovernmental organization in India has connection with educational development and social change. While philanthropy is an instinct that focuses on the human wish to eliminate suffering, it offers no rights to its beneficiaries, who have no recourse against contributors. It contributors. It has observed that in the liberal agenda, NGOs were expected to be more accountable than governments and to perform more efficiently (Sen 1999)Religious gifts are not tax deductible for donors in modern India, and the government currently has no control over them(Agarwal and Dadrawala 2004). Acc. To Tandon (2002).Throughout Indian history, various conceptions of wealth social duty have emerged. Helping those in need was seen as the responsibility of the individual in classical Hinduism rather than being the responsibility of institutions.

NGOs play an important role in development of society along with an economy development as it can be seen that there is a connection between these terms. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have grown in number, size, and scope during the past 20 years and have become important players in social, economic, and political landscapes all over the world (Jamali,2003). Acc. to Vakil(1997), The literature on NGOs faces a definitional and taxonomical conundrum, with some classifying and identifying them based on their organizational and functional characteristics, some focusing on their nature as the ultimate remedy for the state developmental deficiencies(Lewis & Kanji, 2009).

Cluster 4 (Yellow)

Charity, development, religion, social development, inequality and sustainability are some of the important related themes in the field of philanthropy research. Cluster 4, which is yellow in color reflects evidence from Fauzia's (2013) research on trust and the state. Charitable organization are working very hard to gather money to support the poor.

Donations from the general population have diverged from the overall downward trend in charitable giving throughout time. (Eng Ling, 2012). The need for raising money, on the other hand, is growing quickly, and if this issue is not resolved, it could be problematic for those who are struggling (Sargeant et al., 2002). It has noted that Studies on donation and money contribution have added moral norms in along with these two norms to the conventional model that forecasts altruistic action (Warbuton and Terry, 2000; Armitage and Conner, 2001)

Cluster 5

NGOs, charities, inequality, poverty and social development are some of the important related themes in the field of philanthropy. Cluster 5, which is purple in color reflect the link between charity & development because these are the keywords with CO- Occurrence weight 26 and 30 respectively.

Cluster 6

The sixth cluster focused more on corporate social responsibility, corporate philanthropy and CSR. Corporate social responsibility activity and social responsibility were the keywords with highest Co-Occurrence weight of 25, 6, 6, 7 respectively.). As suggested by past researcher, one of the ways for businesses to participate in corporate philanthropy is through corporate social responsibility (CSR). As evidence, ‘corporate philanthropy’ is among the most cited papers when assessing charitable giving such as article by Williams (2003) on ‘Women on Corporate Boards of Directors and their Influence on Corporate Philanthropy’.

Corporate Social Responsibility was more interlinked with the keyword corporate philanthropy (Occurrence weight - 25, link strength- 21).

CSR has evolved from an idea to a reality as a result, and many now believe that it is essential for organizations to identify their social obligations and integrate moral principles into their operations (Lichtenstein et al. 2004). Despite the fact that more businesses follow and display their commitment to CSR (Pinkston and Carroll 1994), many find this endeavor difficult (Lindgreen et al. 2009). In order to strengthen their company’s image in the mind of the public and other stakeholders, businesses are increasingly using CSR initiatives, such as annual reports (Sweeney and Coughlan 2008) and websites (Maignan and Ralston 2002; Wanderley et al. 2008). Literature also questions whether businesses should share information about their CSR projects and, if they do, if traditional methods of marketing are the best option (Van de Ven 2008). However, recent research indicates that sharing information about social activities is not always beneficial to the participating organization, particularly when CSR communication may result in stakeholder; suspicion and cynicism (Mohr et al. 2001; Schlegelmilch and Pollach 2005). Additionally, CSR raises the standard of living for the company workers (as well as their families), the neighborhood, and society at large (Watts and Holme 1999).

Thus, it can be described in the result that there is a relation between stakeholder, social responsibility and corporate philanthropy. The stakeholders changing perceptions and actions reflect a more delicate and widespread awareness of the environmental, social, and labor obligations of corporations (Kassis & Majaj, 2012). To highlight the present situation and possibilities for CSR in India in the future Sundar (2000) depending on the political and economic climate of the nation, split CSR development into four stages. Later on, Chahoud et al. (2007) reinforce him (2000) claiming that the evolution of various CSR practices was synchronized with India historical history. Last but not least, CSR has expanded globally along with the global economy. However, most CSR research is still conducted locally (Lee 2008).

Geographical Distribution

The retrieved 583 articles about philanthropy and development of an economy were obtained from more than 30 countries. Table:2 presented the top 10 countries that contribute 72.89% of the total publication. These countries published 583 documents and received 4,286 citations.

Table:-2 Top-ten countries with the highest number of publications.

Country	Documents	Citation
United States	133	1186
United Kingdom	86	894

China	56	654
Canada	31	287
Australia	30	371
India	27	255
Germany	23	202
Hong kong	14	168
Italy	13	172
Japan	12	79

The United States had the most published articles, followed by United Kingdom, china and Canada. In general, high-income nations dominated the rankings and therefore able to create and publish a greater number of paper because they had adequate resources and the necessary structure, tools, and equipment (Granada, 2022). More importantly, the United States alone also kept on dominating in the impact of its scientific outputs related to philanthropy and economy development, having a total no of 1186 citations, followed by United Kingdom, China and Canada.

Conclusion

This paper employed the properties of systematic review along with bibliometric analysis to examine the present state and trend of the development of scientific outputs that incorporate philanthropy and the related terms in development of an economy. Based on the performance analysis of the 533 retrieved documents from Scopus, the study could claim that this research topic only started in 2015 and that its major research hotspot is associated with the philanthropy or donation.

Although not included in the highly co-occurring topics, it was also unveiled that the philanthropy or charitable giving has been gaining interest and increasingly cited. Moreover, the study also revealed that high-income countries have the greatest contributions towards promoting philanthropy activities. Furthermore, there is still a drought of publications on this topic while many sustainability concerns need to be addressed in this sector.

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